

Improving Organizational Commitment through Analysis of Work Environment, Work Engagement, and Job Satisfaction at PT DPP Jakarta

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Abstract:- Data on the Mercer Indonesia survey in 2022, more than 23,200 employees from local and multinational companies in Indonesia. 30% of employees believe they can seek better and bigger opportunities outside their current organization. This shows that employee organizational commitment is problematic so the purpose of this study is to find out what factors can influence employee organizational commitment so that they can last longer in the company. The population in this study were all permanent employees at PT DPP Jakarta, with a saturated sampling method of 51 respondents. The data analysis method uses SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square). The results of the study found that the work environment has no significant effect on organizational commitment. Work engagement has no significant effect on organizational commitment. Job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment. The results of the work environment and work engagement have a significant effect on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction managed to mediate effectively the work environment variables and work engagement variables on organizational commitment.

Keywords:- *Work Environment, Work Engagement, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) are one of the most important parts of an organization (Hakim and Hidayat, 2018) because they are the ones who will run, direct, and develop the organization according to the goals that have been set from the beginning of the organization. Therefore, human resources must be managed properly so that organizational effectiveness and efficiency are achieved. To achieve this, human resources are required to have an emotional attachment to the organization so that they will accept the values of the organization. The company's human resources must continue to be developed by the company following

the times, so that employees can work in a more professional, responsible manner, besides having a good attitude, in other words, so that goals can be achieved, the company requires highly committed employees (Faishal and Dewi, 2019). Organizational commitment is an important behavioral dimension in assessing employees' desire to remain part of the organization (Sapitri and Suryalena, 2016). Employees who are committed to their organization are people who have loyalty and pride in their organization, so they want to maintain and do a good job (Ghorbanpour, Dehnavi, Heyrani, 2014). Having a high commitment will make employees care about the sustainability of the organization and make efforts to make the organization a better direction.

Mercer Indonesia survey in 2022 in topcareer.id written by Ferdian (2022), Mercer collects data from more than 23,200 employees from local and multinational companies in Indonesia. 30% of the employees surveyed feel that they cannot fulfill their career goals at the company they are in, Employees believe that they can seek better and bigger opportunities outside their current organization, which is why they often choose not to stay longer in the company.

Based on The results of the survey, show that employee organizational commitment is still low and needs more improvement so that they can last a long time in the company even though the survey shows that employees easily leave the company for various reasons. This organizational commitment is a serious problem that must be considered by the company because getting employees who are not committed will also make it difficult for the company to implement its organizational goals. And here the company that is used as the object of research is PT DPP Jakarta, and to show how much organizational commitment this employee has, which is an important issue in the organization, can be seen in the company's employee turnover data table for the last 3 years from 2020-2022 as follows:

Table 1 Data Turnover Employees

Year	Number of employees	Number of Entered Employees	Number of Employees Leaving
2020	81	2	15
2021	68	2	12
2022	58	7	13

Source: Company Secondary Data

Based on employee turnover data for the last 3 years, from 2020 to 2022, it can be seen that employees leaving are higher than employees entering. The tendency of employees to decide to resign is the possibility of getting opportunities in other companies with higher salaries. And it can be said from the employee turnover data, the company has a problem with employee organizational commitment.

Several factors can affect organizational commitment and previous research regarding the relationship between the variables to be studied, there are still inconsistent results as shown in the following table:

Table 2 Research Gap

Relationship		Research Findings	
Independent	Dependent	Influential	Not Influential
Work Environment	Job Satisfaction	Mustagfirin, Wulan, Haryono (2019)	Santoso and Sidik (2019)
Work Engagement	Job Satisfaction	Putra dan Darmastuti (2021)	Fairnandha (2021)
Job Satisfaction	Organizational Commitment	To and Huang (2022)	Curry <i>et al</i> (1986)
Work Environment	Organizational Commitment	Boonsiritomachai, and Sud-On (2021)	Widjaya, Budiono, Bayu (2021)
Work Engagement	Organizational Commitment	Sadikin <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Rameshkumar (2020)

Based on the findings of several studies regarding the variables to be examined in the research, there is still a research gap in the work environment and work engagement studies on organizational commitment through job satisfaction

Based on the description of the background of the problem, the researcher is interested in raising the title "The Effect of Work Engagement and Work Environment on Organizational Commitment through Job Satisfaction As Intervening Variables at PT DPP Jakarta".

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between work environment and work engagement on job satisfaction and organizational commitment, job satisfaction on organizational commitment, and work environment and work engagement on organizational commitment through job satisfaction as a mediating variable.

II. READING REVIEW

➤ *Organizational Commitment*

Suhartini (2018) said organizational commitment is an important behavioral dimension that can be used to assess employee tendencies to remain members of the organization. A committed employee will tend to exert extensive effort on behalf of the organization and have strong aspirations to maintain membership in the organization Rameshkumar (2020).

➤ *Job Satisfaction*

Job satisfaction refers to the overall positive feelings of an employee about his entire job (Mardanov, 2020). Job satisfaction is the fulfillment and joy that a person gets from his job (Singh, Singh, Srivastava, 2020). Aswar, Rivai, and Chaeriah (2022) suggest that job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state with employees see their work.

➤ *Work Environment*

Ningrum, Dian, and Tjiptogoro (2019), the work environment is all the supporting tools and materials used in the environment around a person working, and equipped with work methods and arrangements, both as individuals and groups. The work environment is everything related to physical and psychological aspects that will directly or indirectly affect employees (Suyono, Eliyana, Ratmawati, Elisabeth, 2021).

➤ *Work Engagement*

Work engagement is defined as "a positive, satisfying, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Orgambidez and Almeida, 2019). Vigor refers to having a high level of energy at work, even in the face of obstacles and difficulties. Dedication refers to the professional involvement, inspiration, and pride taken in a job well done. Absorption refers to a high degree of concentration on work tasks.

➤ Framework

Fig 1 Framework

➤ Gambar 1. Theoretical Framework

• Hypothesis:

- ✓ H1: There is a positive and significant effect of the work environment on job satisfaction.
- ✓ H2: There is a positive and significant effect of work engagement on job satisfaction.
- ✓ H3: There is a positive and significant effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment.
- ✓ H4: There is a positive and significant effect of the work environment on organizational commitment.
- ✓ H5: There is a positive and significant effect of work engagement on organizational commitment.
- ✓ H6: There is an indirect and significant effect of work environment on organizational commitment through job satisfaction as a mediating variable.
- ✓ H7: There is an indirect and significant effect of work engagement on organizational commitment through job satisfaction as a mediating variable.

III. STUDY METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach method. The use of unit of analysis in this study is an individual who is in the company where the research object is carried out, namely PT DPP Jakarta. The population used in this study were all company employees, totaling 51 people. Variable operationalization includes work environment (X1) and work engagement (X2) as the independent variable, job satisfaction (Z) as the mediator variable, and organizational commitment (Y) as the dependent variable. The sampling technique used in this study is non-probability sampling, the type of non-probability sampling used in this study is census (saturated) sampling, which is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples (Sugiyono, 2017: 217) in other words, samples in research This amounted to 51 respondents.

This study used primary data in the form of questionnaires which were distributed to employees of PT DPP Jakarta. Questionnaires were distributed to research respondents using the Google Form application assisted by

the Company's HRD. The data analysis technique used in this study is the SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) data analysis technique or the Structural Equation Model where the data processing uses the Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS) program version 3.2.9.

IV. DISCUSSION

➤ Outer Model Measurement Analysis

According to Ghozali (2016), the Outer Model is a model that connects indicators with their latent variables. The validity test measures the suitability or accuracy of an instrument in measurement, so that it can be seen whether the indicators used are appropriate and represent the variables being measured (Ghozali, 2014). Validity test includes convergent validity test by looking at AVE and discriminant validity test by looking at cross loading. Then the other outer model test is the reliability test by looking at Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability. The results of the convergent validity test are by measuring AVE as shown in the table below:

Table 3 Value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Absorption	0.802
Affective	0.723
Co-Workers	0.841
Continuance	0.599
Dedication	0.694
Job Satisfaction	0.587
Lingkungan Kerja Fisik	0.777
Lingkungan Kerja Non Fisik	0.790
Normative	0.763
Organizational Commitment	0.668
Pay	0.739
Promotion	0.821
Supervisor	0.749
Vigor	0.656
Work Engagement	0.618
Work Environment	0.732
Work Itself	0.747

Source: 2023 PLS Results

In Table 3, Average Variant Extracted (AVE), the AVE value for all indicators and latent variables already has a value of more than 0.5 (Ghozali, 2014). So it can be said

that the measurement model is valid and meets the requirements of the convergent validity test.

Table 4 Discriminant Validity Results (Cross Loading)

	AB	AC	CC	CW	D	LKF	LKNF	NC	Pay	Pro	Sup	V	W
AB1	0.872	0.578	0.541	0.55	0.608	0.598	0.658	0.566	0.526	0.617	0.537	0.696	0.646
AB1	0.872	0.578	0.541	0.55	0.608	0.598	0.658	0.566	0.526	0.617	0.537	0.696	0.646
AB2	0.9	0.605	0.585	0.562	0.696	0.586	0.634	0.665	0.582	0.627	0.561	0.802	0.76
AB2	0.9	0.605	0.585	0.562	0.696	0.586	0.634	0.665	0.582	0.627	0.561	0.802	0.76
AB3	0.89	0.583	0.49	0.46	0.608	0.435	0.526	0.546	0.531	0.61	0.42	0.618	0.581
AB3	0.89	0.583	0.49	0.46	0.608	0.435	0.526	0.546	0.531	0.61	0.42	0.618	0.581
AB4	0.919	0.688	0.578	0.434	0.726	0.605	0.653	0.696	0.637	0.626	0.517	0.752	0.718
AB4	0.919	0.688	0.578	0.434	0.726	0.605	0.653	0.696	0.637	0.626	0.517	0.752	0.718
AC1	0.606	0.842	0.765	0.708	0.614	0.69	0.689	0.655	0.725	0.609	0.719	0.611	0.662
AC1	0.606	0.842	0.765	0.708	0.614	0.69	0.689	0.655	0.725	0.609	0.719	0.611	0.662
AC2	0.619	0.919	0.763	0.574	0.746	0.652	0.584	0.723	0.722	0.6	0.68	0.672	0.726
AC2	0.619	0.919	0.763	0.574	0.746	0.652	0.584	0.723	0.722	0.6	0.68	0.672	0.726
AC3	0.654	0.844	0.669	0.622	0.721	0.727	0.649	0.663	0.646	0.568	0.654	0.648	0.683
AC3	0.654	0.844	0.669	0.622	0.721	0.727	0.649	0.663	0.646	0.568	0.654	0.648	0.683
AC4	0.603	0.844	0.661	0.52	0.724	0.674	0.721	0.88	0.726	0.671	0.736	0.724	0.761
AC4	0.603	0.844	0.661	0.52	0.724	0.674	0.721	0.88	0.726	0.671	0.736	0.724	0.761
AC5	0.427	0.798	0.607	0.362	0.596	0.489	0.494	0.646	0.622	0.502	0.53	0.53	0.544
AC5	0.427	0.798	0.607	0.362	0.596	0.489	0.494	0.646	0.622	0.502	0.53	0.53	0.544
CC1	0.375	0.503	0.774	0.543	0.393	0.43	0.384	0.439	0.566	0.417	0.491	0.389	0.462
CC2	0.413	0.475	0.712	0.548	0.409	0.559	0.436	0.379	0.557	0.329	0.463	0.463	0.532
CC3	0.513	0.726	0.842	0.498	0.525	0.689	0.685	0.653	0.742	0.484	0.606	0.612	0.655
CC3	0.513	0.726	0.842	0.498	0.525	0.689	0.685	0.653	0.742	0.484	0.606	0.612	0.655
CC4	0.549	0.725	0.764	0.448	0.67	0.49	0.571	0.804	0.618	0.565	0.644	0.56	0.614
CC4	0.549	0.725	0.764	0.448	0.67	0.49	0.571	0.804	0.618	0.565	0.644	0.56	0.614
CW1	0.612	0.591	0.536	0.906	0.591	0.542	0.624	0.553	0.443	0.665	0.708	0.639	0.629
CW1	0.612	0.591	0.536	0.906	0.591	0.542	0.624	0.553	0.443	0.665	0.708	0.639	0.629
CW2	0.456	0.644	0.627	0.919	0.519	0.679	0.671	0.498	0.537	0.492	0.687	0.582	0.674
CW2	0.456	0.644	0.627	0.919	0.519	0.679	0.671	0.498	0.537	0.492	0.687	0.582	0.674
CW3	0.469	0.569	0.6	0.926	0.557	0.61	0.691	0.496	0.465	0.453	0.622	0.549	0.655
CW3	0.469	0.569	0.6	0.926	0.557	0.61	0.691	0.496	0.465	0.453	0.622	0.549	0.655
D1	0.629	0.622	0.572	0.466	0.845	0.552	0.524	0.65	0.456	0.644	0.496	0.712	0.583
D1	0.629	0.622	0.572	0.466	0.845	0.552	0.524	0.65	0.456	0.644	0.496	0.712	0.583
D2	0.489	0.535	0.465	0.525	0.808	0.486	0.49	0.586	0.373	0.596	0.585	0.692	0.583
D2	0.489	0.535	0.465	0.525	0.808	0.486	0.49	0.586	0.373	0.596	0.585	0.692	0.583
D3	0.665	0.691	0.588	0.618	0.828	0.727	0.74	0.769	0.588	0.588	0.676	0.79	0.762
D3	0.665	0.691	0.588	0.618	0.828	0.727	0.74	0.769	0.588	0.588	0.676	0.79	0.762
D4	0.707	0.738	0.567	0.476	0.829	0.679	0.674	0.632	0.533	0.629	0.566	0.752	0.734
D4	0.707	0.738	0.567	0.476	0.829	0.679	0.674	0.632	0.533	0.629	0.566	0.752	0.734
D5	0.573	0.744	0.603	0.438	0.855	0.624	0.625	0.798	0.515	0.638	0.611	0.695	0.693
D5	0.573	0.744	0.603	0.438	0.855	0.624	0.625	0.798	0.515	0.638	0.611	0.695	0.693
LKF1	0.467	0.7	0.619	0.61	0.683	0.876	0.744	0.592	0.561	0.491	0.594	0.62	0.687
LKF1	0.467	0.7	0.619	0.61	0.683	0.876	0.744	0.592	0.561	0.491	0.594	0.62	0.687
LKF2	0.614	0.644	0.637	0.534	0.681	0.852	0.736	0.656	0.699	0.659	0.615	0.775	0.728
LKF2	0.614	0.644	0.637	0.534	0.681	0.852	0.736	0.656	0.699	0.659	0.615	0.775	0.728
LKF3	0.57	0.673	0.611	0.615	0.601	0.915	0.813	0.633	0.658	0.551	0.63	0.686	0.718
LKF3	0.57	0.673	0.611	0.615	0.601	0.915	0.813	0.633	0.658	0.551	0.63	0.686	0.718
LKNF1	0.588	0.638	0.583	0.633	0.685	0.786	0.898	0.617	0.548	0.495	0.618	0.729	0.753
LKNF1	0.588	0.638	0.583	0.633	0.685	0.786	0.898	0.617	0.548	0.495	0.618	0.729	0.753
LKNF2	0.632	0.728	0.706	0.717	0.646	0.74	0.878	0.743	0.695	0.654	0.728	0.702	0.732
LKNF2	0.632	0.728	0.706	0.717	0.646	0.74	0.878	0.743	0.695	0.654	0.728	0.702	0.732
LKNF3	0.625	0.612	0.572	0.577	0.633	0.788	0.892	0.583	0.636	0.511	0.561	0.683	0.711
LKNF3	0.625	0.612	0.572	0.577	0.633	0.788	0.892	0.583	0.636	0.511	0.561	0.683	0.711
NC1	0.637	0.719	0.593	0.635	0.761	0.568	0.638	0.815	0.541	0.748	0.707	0.709	0.725

NC1	0.637	0.719	0.593	0.635	0.761	0.568	0.638	0.815	0.541	0.748	0.707	0.709	0.725
NC2	0.62	0.729	0.754	0.463	0.734	0.65	0.617	0.906	0.635	0.699	0.684	0.718	0.688
NC2	0.62	0.729	0.754	0.463	0.734	0.65	0.617	0.906	0.635	0.699	0.684	0.718	0.688
NC3	0.498	0.742	0.643	0.337	0.699	0.553	0.528	0.861	0.552	0.582	0.649	0.651	0.582
NC3	0.498	0.742	0.643	0.337	0.699	0.553	0.528	0.861	0.552	0.582	0.649	0.651	0.582
NC4	0.671	0.759	0.734	0.539	0.698	0.707	0.756	0.908	0.758	0.734	0.75	0.716	0.746
NC4	0.671	0.759	0.734	0.539	0.698	0.707	0.756	0.908	0.758	0.734	0.75	0.716	0.746
Pay1	0.503	0.633	0.671	0.453	0.48	0.686	0.663	0.569	0.866	0.486	0.58	0.657	0.685
Pay1	0.503	0.633	0.671	0.453	0.48	0.686	0.663	0.569	0.866	0.486	0.58	0.657	0.685
Pay2	0.657	0.777	0.784	0.464	0.616	0.652	0.655	0.726	0.886	0.565	0.539	0.63	0.683
Pay2	0.657	0.777	0.784	0.464	0.616	0.652	0.655	0.726	0.886	0.565	0.539	0.63	0.683
Pay3	0.472	0.683	0.632	0.439	0.425	0.515	0.475	0.534	0.827	0.432	0.414	0.403	0.507
Pro1	0.611	0.481	0.42	0.588	0.585	0.594	0.61	0.584	0.427	0.859	0.483	0.635	0.563
Pro2	0.625	0.655	0.571	0.487	0.734	0.567	0.525	0.79	0.528	0.937	0.627	0.684	0.62
Pro2	0.625	0.655	0.571	0.487	0.734	0.567	0.525	0.79	0.528	0.937	0.627	0.684	0.62
Pro3	0.646	0.741	0.628	0.531	0.692	0.588	0.56	0.759	0.608	0.92	0.645	0.641	0.589
Pro3	0.646	0.741	0.628	0.531	0.692	0.588	0.56	0.759	0.608	0.92	0.645	0.641	0.589
Sup1	0.457	0.682	0.697	0.659	0.566	0.615	0.629	0.743	0.548	0.593	0.892	0.605	0.661
Sup1	0.457	0.682	0.697	0.659	0.566	0.615	0.629	0.743	0.548	0.593	0.892	0.605	0.661
Sup2	0.505	0.616	0.523	0.56	0.621	0.63	0.623	0.708	0.429	0.635	0.863	0.648	0.597
Sup2	0.505	0.616	0.523	0.56	0.621	0.63	0.623	0.708	0.429	0.635	0.863	0.648	0.597
Sup3	0.52	0.733	0.668	0.683	0.644	0.562	0.601	0.621	0.575	0.463	0.84	0.662	0.702
Sup3	0.52	0.733	0.668	0.683	0.644	0.562	0.601	0.621	0.575	0.463	0.84	0.662	0.702
V1	0.637	0.682	0.653	0.626	0.702	0.728	0.753	0.627	0.659	0.472	0.605	0.843	0.71
V1	0.637	0.682	0.653	0.626	0.702	0.728	0.753	0.627	0.659	0.472	0.605	0.843	0.71
V2	0.714	0.677	0.548	0.573	0.741	0.618	0.615	0.603	0.531	0.632	0.571	0.817	0.636
V2	0.714	0.677	0.548	0.573	0.741	0.618	0.615	0.603	0.531	0.632	0.571	0.817	0.636
V3	0.767	0.548	0.579	0.563	0.781	0.651	0.716	0.664	0.523	0.581	0.642	0.856	0.68
V3	0.767	0.548	0.579	0.563	0.781	0.651	0.716	0.664	0.523	0.581	0.642	0.856	0.68
V4	0.66	0.399	0.385	0.422	0.532	0.503	0.515	0.529	0.43	0.576	0.408	0.773	0.588
V4	0.66	0.399	0.385	0.422	0.532	0.503	0.515	0.529	0.43	0.576	0.408	0.773	0.588
V5	0.468	0.657	0.519	0.45	0.728	0.593	0.557	0.664	0.498	0.515	0.667	0.74	0.718
V5	0.468	0.657	0.519	0.45	0.728	0.593	0.557	0.664	0.498	0.515	0.667	0.74	0.718
V6	0.64	0.687	0.564	0.481	0.754	0.711	0.672	0.791	0.591	0.722	0.678	0.822	0.725
V6	0.64	0.687	0.564	0.481	0.754	0.711	0.672	0.791	0.591	0.722	0.678	0.822	0.725
W1	0.638	0.675	0.601	0.718	0.612	0.641	0.63	0.6	0.59	0.596	0.666	0.661	0.849
W1	0.638	0.675	0.601	0.718	0.612	0.641	0.63	0.6	0.59	0.596	0.666	0.661	0.849
W2	0.679	0.744	0.724	0.469	0.797	0.671	0.671	0.716	0.68	0.494	0.6	0.756	0.833
W2	0.679	0.744	0.724	0.469	0.797	0.671	0.671	0.716	0.68	0.494	0.6	0.756	0.833
W3	0.657	0.658	0.616	0.648	0.698	0.775	0.829	0.722	0.642	0.596	0.691	0.75	0.91
W3	0.657	0.658	0.616	0.648	0.698	0.775	0.829	0.722	0.642	0.596	0.691	0.75	0.91

Source: 2023 PLS Results

In Table 4 the cross-loading values for most indicators of each latent variable are greater than the values of the other latent variables (Ghozali, 2014). This means that each latent variable has good discriminant validity.

Table 5 Reliability Test Results (Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability)

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Absorption	0.917	0.942
Affective	0.904	0.929
Co-Workers	0.905	0.941
Continuance	0.787	0.856
Dedication	0.890	0.919
Job Satisfaction	0.941	0.949
Lingkungan Kerja Fisik	0.856	0.913
Lingkungan Kerja Non Fisik	0.867	0.919
Normative	0.896	0.928
Organizational Commitment	0.950	0.957

Pay	0.824	0.895
Promotion	0.890	0.932
Supervisor	0.832	0.899
Vigor	0.894	0.919
Work Engagement	0.955	0.960
Work Environment	0.927	0.942
Work Itself	0.830	0.899

Source: 2023 PLS Results

In Table 5 the Composite Reliability value is greater than 0.7 (Ghozali, 2015), work engagement has the best score on composite reliability of 0.960 and continuance has the lowest score on composite reliability of 0.856. Meanwhile, the Cronbach Alpha value also shows that a value of more than 0.6 (Ghozali, 2015) means that all variables are reliable and have met the test requirements. Work engagement has the best score on composite reliability of 0.955 and continuance has the lowest score on composite reliability of 0.787. Based on the results of the reliability test, it means that the construct has a strong reliability value, or the questionnaire is used as a consistent and reliable research tool based on these findings (Ghozali, 2015).

➤ *Inner Model Measurement Analysis*

A structural model test (inner model) is used to test the relationship between constructs or latent variables by looking at the parameter coefficient estimates. The feasibility test of this model can be seen from the R-square, F-square, and Q-square values.

Table 6 Result of R-square value (R²)

	R-Square
Organizational Commitment	0,816
Job Satisfaction	0,818

Source: 2023 PLS Results

From Table 6 the model suitability test can be seen the results of R². Organizational commitment has a value of 0.816 (81.6%) meaning that organizational commitment can be explained by the independent variable of 81.6%, the rest is explained by other variables not examined in this study. While the variable job satisfaction is worth 0.818 (81.8%) meaning that job satisfaction can be explained by the independent variable of 81.8% and the rest is explained by other variables not examined in this study. So the r-square value on organizational commitment and job satisfaction variables is strong (Ghozali, 2015).

Table 7 Results of F-Square Values (F²)

	Job Satisfaction	Organizational Commitment
Work Engagement	0.45	0.076
Work Environment	0.43	0.001
Job Satisfaction		0.461

Source: 2023 PLS Results

Based on Table 7 of the f-square results above, it can be seen that the work engagement and work environment variables can have a large effect on job satisfaction as seen from the f-square value which is more than 0.35. while work engagement and work environment only have a small effect on organizational commitment as seen from the f-square value which is less than 0.15, but job satisfaction has a large effect on organizational commitment as seen from the f-square value which is more than 0.35.

Table 8 Q-square (Q²) Value Results

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Job Satisfaction	663	373.996	0.436
Organizational Commitment	561	269.115	0.520

Source: 2023 PLS Results

A q-square value greater than 0 (zero) will show that the model has a predictive relevance value, whereas if the Q² value is less than 0 (zero) it will show that the model lacks predictive relevance (Ghozali Source: 2023 PLS Results, 2015). From the results of the Q² test, it was found that the Q² values of the compiled models were all > 0 so the model was declared to have met predictive relevance where the model had been properly reconstructed.

➤ *Hypothesis Test Measurement*

In testing the hypothesis there is a significant value between variables this significant value is obtained through a bootstrapping procedure. Looking at the significance of the hypothesis is seen from the parameter coefficient values and the significance value of the t-statistic on the bootstrapping report algorithm. To find out whether there is a significant relationship or not, it can be seen from the p-value <0.05 or t-table at alpha 0.05 (5%) = 1.96 then the t-table is compared to the t-count > 1.96, so the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 9 Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
Work Environment -> Job Satisfaction	0.471	4.019	0.000
Work Engagement -> Job Satisfaction	0.483	4.666	0.000
Job Satisfaction -> Organizational Commitment	0.677	3.959	0.000
Work Environment -> Organizational Commitment	0.021	0.122	0.905
Work Engagement -> Organizational Commitment	0.238	1.376	0.170

Source: 2023 PLS Results

Table 10 Indirect Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
Work Environment -> Job Satisfaction -> Organizational Commitment	0.319	2.544	0.011
Work Engagement -> Job Satisfaction -> Organizational Commitment	0.327	3.337	0.001

Source: 2023 PLS Results

Fig 2 Inner Model Bootstrapping Results

➤ Discussion Result

The work environment variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction variable (Z) with a parameter coefficient of 0.471 and a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05, in this case, the H1 hypothesis is accepted. This means that the more there is an improvement in the work environment, the more satisfaction will increase. These results are in line with several previous studies by Taheri et al. (2020) that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Then there is Mustagfirin et al. (2019) who say that the work environment has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction.

The work engagement variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction variable (Z) with a parameter coefficient of 0.483 and a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05, in this case, the H2 hypothesis is accepted. This shows that a higher level of work engagement among employees will have a positive impact on increasing job satisfaction. These results are the same as previous studies by Putra and Darmastuti (2021) work engagement has a positive effect on job satisfaction. The same results were also obtained by researchers who had carried out by Lahat and Marthanti (2021) work engagement has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The variable job satisfaction (Z) has a positive and significant effect on the variable organizational commitment (Y) with the magnitude of the influence of the parameter coefficient of 0.677 and the resulting p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$, in this case, the H3 hypothesis is accepted. This means that as employee job satisfaction increases, the positive impact of increasing employee organizational commitment will also increase. And the results of this study are in line with previous studies by To and Huang (2022) job satisfaction has a positive effect on organizational commitment. Based on research conducted by Bashir and Gani (2020) job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment.

The work environment variable (X1) has a positive and insignificant effect on the organizational commitment variable (Y) with the magnitude of the influence of the parameter coefficient of 0.021 and the resulting p-value of $0.905 > 0.05$, in this case, the H4 hypothesis is rejected. This means that the results of the researcher's research are following Widjaya et al. (2021) who found that there is no significant effect of the work environment on organizational commitment. However, this is contrary to previous research conducted by Faishal and Dewi (2019) which stated that the work environment has a positive effect on organizational commitment. Then there are the research findings of Gunawan and Ardana (2020) which mean that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at Artha Agung Resort and Restaurant.

The work engagement variable (X2) has a positive and insignificant effect on the organizational commitment variable (Y) with the magnitude of the influence of the parameter coefficient of 0.238 and the resulting p-value of $0.170 > 0.05$, in this case, the H5 hypothesis is rejected. These results follow Rameshkumar (2020) but are different from previous scientific findings that have been carried out by several researchers such as Boonsiritomachai and Sud-On (2022) who found work engagement has a positive effect on organizational commitment. Then some further researchers have found work engagement to have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

The work environment variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the organizational commitment (Y) variable mediated by job satisfaction (Z) with the magnitude of the influence of the parameter coefficient of 0.319 and the resulting p-value of $0.011 < 0.05$, in this case, the H6 hypothesis is accepted. The results of this data processing, mean that job satisfaction can mediate effectively the influence of the work environment on organizational commitment. This shows the perception that the better the work environment owned by PT DPP, the more organizational commitment will increase and to further strengthen this it is also necessary to increase job satisfaction for PT DPP employees with a high level of employee job satisfaction. long time in the company. This is in line with research by Martini and Susanto (2021) who found in their research that the work environment has a

significant effect on organizational commitment through job satisfaction.

The work engagement variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the organizational commitment variable (Y) mediated by job satisfaction (Z) with the magnitude of the influence of the parameter coefficient of 0.327 and the resulting p-value of $0.001 < 0.05$, in this case, the H7 hypothesis is accepted. This means that the higher the level of work engagement possessed by employees, the higher the organizational commitment of employees. In line with that, an increase in employee job satisfaction will indirectly help increase employee organizational commitment to the Company. The results of this data processing mean that job satisfaction can mediate effectively the effect of work engagement on organizational commitment. This is in line with previous research conducted by Yan, X et al. (2019) the higher the level of work engagement associated with more job satisfaction, and by Putra and Darmastuti (2021) work engagement has a positive effect on job satisfaction. And regarding the link between increased job satisfaction, it will have an impact on organizational commitment. To and Huang's research (2022) found that job satisfaction has a positive effect on organizational commitment, and Bashir and Gani (2020) job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings in this study provide the view that work environment and work engagement do not have a significant impact on organizational commitment. On the other hand, some variables have a significant and large impact, such as the impact of increasing work engagement and work environment on organizational commitment, then there is an increase in job satisfaction, which will further increase organizational commitment by making employees stay longer in the company. And finally, there is the indirect impact of work environment and work engagement on organizational commitment mediated by job satisfaction.

Companies need to create employee loyalty such as being able to foster a sense of love and pride for the company, This can be done by giving employees jobs that match their passion, so they don't feel burdened with the tasks that will be accepted, a comfortable work environment such as superiors and supportive co-workers. Two-way communication with employees and one-way transparency of the reward system that will be obtained by employees from the results of their work performance and salary increases that will be obtained if the work exceeds the target. Improving the physical work environment system for employees such as companies can start by revamping the office interior. Based on the results of the research in this study, there are still other possible independent variables that can influence the dependent variable in this study. The next suggestion is that it is expected to be able to conduct research with a larger sample from a variety of industries because this study only examines one research object and uses a research sample of less than 100 because the results

of this study cannot be said to represent a theory or existing hypothesis.

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